

Supporting Information for ”Do we really know by how much ellipsoidal shapes enhance the extinction of solar radiation by dust?”

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Introduction

Supplementary figures include global maps of annual mean dust optical depth (DOD) and single-scattering albedo (Fig. S1) along with shortwave (Fig. S2), longwave (Fig. S3) and net (shortwave plus longwave; Fig. S4) direct radiative effects by dust, at the top of atmosphere, in the atmosphere and at the surface, presented separately for the two shape experiments (SPH and ELL in the main article).

In Fig. S5 (panels a, b, and c), an approximate estimate of size-distributed amplifications of the DOD at $0.550\ \mu\text{m}$ from the ellipsoidal model (ELL) due to extreme ellipsoids not included in the database of Meng et al. (2010) (ELL-E) is presented. Following Huang, Kok, Saito, and Muñoz (2023), we estimate the single-shape extinction efficiency of missing ellipsoids with constant height-to-width ratio (HWR) and increasing length-to-width ratios (LWR), the latter based on the same sampling used in MengDB up to a maximum of 3, by uniformly applying a scaling factor to the last available extinction efficiency for each original HWR. (In this offline calculation, a shape-weighting method consistent with that used in the model, but slightly different in the sampling of the axis ratio domains, is used.) Additionally, the shape-induced increase of asymmetry parameter across the size bins of ModelE2.1 is shown in Fig. S5-d.

Supplementary tables report information about the complex refractive index, at ultraviolet and visible wavelengths, used for dust in our experiments with ModelE2.1 (Table S1, and the selected AERONET stations with dust-dominated retrievals (Table S2).

References

- Huang, Y., Kok, J. F., Saito, M., & Muñoz, O. (2023). Single-scattering properties of ellipsoidal dust aerosols constrained by measured dust shape distributions. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, *23*(4), 2557–2577. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-23-2557-2023>
- Meng, Z., Yang, P., Kattawar, G. W., Bi, L., Liou, K. N., & Laszlo, I. (2010). Single-scattering properties of tri-axial ellipsoidal mineral dust aerosols: A database for application to radiative transfer calculations. *Journal of Aerosol Science*, *41*(5), 501–512. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaerosci.2010.02.008>

Figure S1. Annual mean optical depth (τ) (a and b) and single-scattering albedo (ω) (c and d), based upon a 30-year climatology of modeled dust from the spherical (SPH) and ellipsoidal (ELL) experiments. The optical properties are averaged over the spectral band of ModelE2.1 covering ultraviolet and visible wavelengths (0.30–0.77 μm). The extremes of the color bars are set to the 1st and 99th percentiles of the mapped variables. Global means along with minimum and maximum (within parentheses) are also reported.

Figure S2. Annual mean shortwave direct radiative effect at the top of atmosphere ($R_{\text{toa}}^{\text{sw}}$) (a and b), in the atmosphere ($R_{\text{atm}}^{\text{sw}}$) (c and d) and at the surface ($R_{\text{sfc}}^{\text{sw}}$) (e and f), based upon a 30-year climatology of modeled dust from the spherical (SPH) and ellipsoidal (ELL) experiments. The extremes of the color bars are set to the 1st and 99th percentiles of the mapped variables. Global means along with minimum and maximum (within parentheses) are also reported.

Figure S3. Same as Fig. S2 but showing the longwave direct radiative effect.

Figure S4. Same as Fig. S2 but showing the net direct radiative effect (shortwave plus longwave).

Figure S5. *Panels a, b and c:* Increase of global annual mean dust optical depth (DOD) at 0.550 μm , across the size bins of ModelE2.1, in the enhanced ellipsoidal case (ELL-E) compared to the control ellipsoidal case (ELL). While ELL is based only upon the ellipsoids included in MengDB (the case analyzed in the manuscript), the ELL-E case is a test calculation that estimates the impact of highly aspherical ellipsoids not represented in MengDB upon the DOD and thus the shortwave direct radiative effect. The different panels show calculations corresponding to scaling factors of extinction efficiency (F_{mis}) of 0% (a), 10% (b) and 20% (c). The variation of DOD summed over all sizes (Δ_{rel}) is also reported. *Panel d:* Shape-induced variation in the asymmetry parameter in the visible band across the size bins of ModelE2.1, along with the bulk relative variation (weighted by scattering optical depth) of the ELL case compared to the control spherical case (SPH).

Table S1. Prescribed real and imaginary refractive indices ($n_o + ik_o$) for dust at wavelengths covering the ultraviolet-visible band of ModelE2.1 (0.30–0.77 μm). The same values are used in both our shape experiments.

λ (μm)	$n_o + ik_o$	λ (μm)	$n_o + ik_o$
0.300	$1.600 + i8.700 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.525	$1.561 + i1.600 \cdot 10^{-3}$
0.325	$1.595 + i7.000 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.550	$1.558 + i1.400 \cdot 10^{-3}$
0.350	$1.590 + i5.800 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.575	$1.555 + i1.200 \cdot 10^{-3}$
0.375	$1.585 + i4.600 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.600	$1.553 + i1.100 \cdot 10^{-3}$
0.400	$1.580 + i3.600 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.625	$1.551 + i9.000 \cdot 10^{-4}$
0.425	$1.576 + i2.900 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.650	$1.550 + i8.000 \cdot 10^{-4}$
0.450	$1.572 + i2.400 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.675	$1.548 + i7.000 \cdot 10^{-4}$
0.475	$1.568 + i2.000 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.700	$1.544 + i7.000 \cdot 10^{-4}$
0.500	$1.564 + i1.800 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.800	$1.540 + i8.000 \cdot 10^{-4}$

Table S2. AERONET stations with dust-dominated retrievals.

Station	Latitude	Longitude
Agoufou	+15.35	-1.48
Banizoumbou	+13.55	+2.67
Cape_San_Juan	+18.38	-65.62
Capo_Verde	+16.73	-22.94
DMN_Maine_Soroa	+13.22	+12.02
Dakar	+14.39	-16.96
Dushanbe	+38.55	+68.86
Eilat	+29.50	+34.92
El_Farafra	+27.06	+27.99
Gandhi_College	+25.87	+84.13
Granada	+37.16	-3.61
Hamim	+22.97	+54.30
IASBS	+36.71	+48.51
IER_Cinzana	+13.28	-5.93
Ilorin	+8.48	+4.67
Izana	+28.31	-16.50
Jaipur	+26.91	+75.81
KAUST_Campus	+22.30	+39.10
Kanpur	+26.51	+80.23
Karachi	+24.95	+67.14
Kuwait_University	+29.33	+47.97
La_Laguna	+28.48	-16.32
La_Parguera	+17.97	-67.05
Lahore	+31.48	+74.26
Medenine-IRA	+33.50	+10.64
Mezaira	+23.10	+53.75
Mussafa	+24.37	+54.47
Ouagadougou	+12.42	-1.49
Ouarzazate	+30.93	-6.91
SEDE_BOKER	+30.85	+34.78
Saada	+31.63	-8.16
Santa_Cruz_Tenerife	+28.47	-16.25
Solar_Village	+24.91	+46.40
Tamanrasset_INM	+22.79	+5.53
Teide	+28.27	-16.64
Tinga_Tingana	-28.98	+139.99
Trelew	-43.25	-65.31
Zinder_Airport	+13.78	+8.99